

Recommended citation: Kiviluoma, P., & Jaakma, K. (2017). Online Support of Project-Based Learning . In Quadrado, J. C., Bernardino, J., & Rocha, J. (Eds.), *Education Excellence for Sustainability. SEFI 45th Annual Conference* (pp. 819-819). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Azores, Portugal. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14698267.

Online Support of Project-based Learning

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ABSTRACT

Project based learning is widely used teaching method in engineering education. In addition to learning substance knowledge projects make it possible to develop ever so important work life expertise such as teamwork and organizing skills. Students are also motivated by projects because they have the possibility to put their knowledge in practice. For teachers project based teaching is often laborious effort, which requires many resources. There are also numerous challenges in projects courses starting from unsystematic progression of the projects and unclear instructions and ending to various social and communicational issues. Based on a survey, students consider open formed tasks, challenges in getting started, management of time, division of tasks and internal communication of the project team as major challenges in project work. Many times the interest of both teacher and students in project work is focused on the outcome of the project instead of the process and learning.

In this study, approaches to supporting different phases of students' projects with online tools are presented. Methods to help, for example, the team formation and communication, project management, documentation and reflection on learning were tested on several engineering project courses. Tools include online forms and questionnaires, video support material and video reports and online self-assessment.

Students' perceptions of the suitability and usefulness of the tested methods were surveyed using online questionnaires during the courses. The results provide us basic principles to utilize online tools in project-based courses. Students prefer multimedia instruction and clear description of the learning process during the project. In addition, the project reporting should be targeted to support future student projects. This study helps us to develop the guidance of the projects. Better-structured project instruction also makes it possible to change teacher's role from a project manager to enabler of the learning.